

A DEGENERATED SHELL ELEMENT FOR THE STATIC LINEAR ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to present the formulation and results of a new shell element based on the degeneration concept that is more suitable to study sandwich shells. This formulation is based on a layerwise assumed - displacement scheme where each layer can deform locally. This allows for a direct computation of realistic transverse shear stresses at the midsurface of each layer without the use of shear - correction factors. Two numerical examples, one of a laminated sandwich plate and another of a isotropic shell show that this approach is well suitable for the analysis of symmetric and nonsymmetric sandwich as well as isotropic shells.

1. INTRODUCTION

The greater part of sandwich configurations are a three-layer type of laminate where a, relatively weak, low-density core supports and stabilizes thin layers of high stiffness facings. Sandwich laminates are very efficient in bending, due to the separation of stiff facings with a thick core without significant increase in weight. This separation produces, nonetheless, high susceptibility to local instabilities. Analytical solutions for several plate situations are reviewed by Allen[1]. Transverse shear deformations occur to a certain extent in any plate subjected to transverse loading, but they are more significant in thick isotropic or laminated composite plates and in sandwich plates with soft cores. In most of the situations, the stress distributions can be very different from those obtained with thin plate Kirchhoff theory. Early theoretical work considering the effects of transverse shear deformations on homogeneous plates was carried out by Reissner [2] and Mindlin [3]. The popularity of the Reissner-Mindlin element type arises partly from the simplicity in the formulation which requires only C^0 displacement continuity, and partly from its general applicability to both thin and thick plates or shells[4,5]. The first order Reissner-Mindlin elements may work well for laminated plates, but Khatua and Cheung [6] have shown that the assumption of constant shear strain may not be suitable for sandwich construction of multiple cores. For laminated plates, we may include some earlier developments: those of Barros [7], Figueiras [8], Ferreira et al.[9], Noor and Mathers [10], Panda and Natarajan [11], Reddy [12], and Lakshminarayana and Murthy [13]. Refined elements based on piece-wise linear layers' inplane displacements with full layer-compatibility were developed by Mawenya and Davies [14], Ferreira et al.[15] for static analysis and by Owen and Li [16, 17] for static, vibration and stability analysis. In these isoparametric elements all five stress components are considered in the individual layers. References [14,15] use the normal rotations of layers as degrees of freedom, whereas references [16,17] use the inplane displacements at both faces of the layers. In the latter approach, the displacements can be eliminated layer by layer, thus leaving those associated with the top surface of the plate as master degrees of freedom. Most of the elements discussed above are characterized by assumed linear or piece-wise linear displacements in the cross-section, and where the nodal degrees of freedom include only displacements or rotations. Higher order elements for thick

laminated plates, in the present context, allow for non-linear warping of the plate cross-section by using extra degrees of freedom. This warping function is often selected to achieve a more realistic distribution of transverse shear stresses vanishing at the exterior surfaces. In addition to the use of extra degrees of freedom, higher order elements involve higher order resultant moments and stresses which have little physical meaning. Quadratic warping functions were used by Engblom and Ochoa[18], with shear stresses being obtained by integration of the equilibrium equation. Parabolic variation of transverse shear strains was assumed by Phan and Reddy [19] for plates. Since the warping functions chosen contain first derivatives of w , both of these elements require C^1 displacement continuity. In contrast, the formulation proposed by Pandya and Kant [20], also of parabolic shear distribution, needs only C^0 continuity. In the model which will be described in this paper, it is assumed that each layer (skin or core) can rotate independently. With this assumption, each layer can deform locally, being this a more accurate model for high-stress gradient areas. In each layer, transverse shear deformation is considered by the imposition of Mindlin-type kinematic relations. In the displacement-based finite-element model, each node possesses 9 degrees of freedom, three displacements of the shell middle-surface and two rotations of the normal of each layer middle-surface. Displacement continuity at the interfaces is imposed. The transverse shear stresses at the middle-surface of the layers are accurately computed, although constant in each layer. However, in this model shear correction factors are not used, which simplifies the usual Mindlin-type models, in which these factors are typically calculated through cylindrical bending assumptions. In this paper, the three-layer sandwich shell element formulation for linear static analysis will be described. The eight and nine-noded isoparametric shell elements (serendipity, lagrangian and heterosis) are included. Numerical examples are discussed in order to access the model accuracy. It is shown that this model is well suited for the analysis of sandwich laminated plates or shells, either isotropic or with very different materials through the thickness.

2. FORMULATION

In modelling a layered structure like a sandwich shell, one usually proceeds to a kind of homogeneization to account for all the kinematic effects (membrane, bending, shear and interactions). However, this procedure does not capture completely the local effects of heterogeneous, highly non-symmetric sandwich structures. We propose a more accurate formulation which considers a three-layer shell (figure 1), in which all layers can locally deform and the shear deformation effects in each layer are considered. The present approach is an extension of the work of Figueiras[8] in laminated composite shells in which the details on the original shell element can be found. In the new degenerated three-layer sandwich shell element each node has nine degrees of freedom, i.e., three translational displacements in the direction of global axes and two rotations for each layer i $\alpha_{1k}^i, \alpha_{2k}^i, i=1,2,3$ with respect to axes in the plane of the midsurface as shown in figure 1. The displacements at any point in the shell element are defined by three Cartesian components of the midsurface node displacements u_k^0 and two rotations of the nodal vector V_k^3 about the orthogonal directions normal to it, in each of the three layers. In layers 1 and 3 (bottom and top facings), the displacement field is defined by

$$u^i = \sum_{k=1}^n N_k(\xi, \eta) u_k^0 + \sum_{k=1}^n N_k(\xi, \eta) (\bar{z} - \bar{z}_i^*) (V_k^1 \alpha_{1k}^i - V_k^2 \alpha_{2k}^i) + \sum_{k=1}^n N_k(\xi, \eta) \bar{z}_i^* (V_k^1 \alpha_{1k}^2 - V_k^2 \alpha_{2k}^2) \quad (1)$$

Expression (1) simplifies for the second layer (core)

$$u^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n N_k(\xi, \eta) u_k^0 + \sum_{k=1}^n N_k(\xi, \eta) \bar{z} (V_k^1 \alpha_{1k}^2 - V_k^2 \alpha_{2k}^2) \quad (2)$$

where N^k are typical shape functions [8], u_k^0 is the vector of displacements of the k^{th} nodal point in Cartesian coordinates and $\alpha_{1k}^i, \alpha_{2k}^i, i=1,2,3$ are the rotations of the i^{th} layer about V_k^2 and V_k^1 respectively [8]. The thickness coordinate \bar{z} is defined as

$$\bar{z} = \zeta \frac{h_k}{2} \quad (3)$$

where h_k is the k^{th} nodal point thickness and $\zeta \in [-1, 1]$ the natural coordinate. The thickness coordinates for the inner layer is taken as zero and for the outer layers as the distance of the layer interfaces to the midsurface:

$$\bar{z}_1^* = -\left(\frac{h_k}{2} - h_k^1\right); \bar{z}_2^* = 0.0; \bar{z}_3^* = \frac{h_k}{2} - h_k^3 \quad (4)$$

where h_k^i is the k^{th} nodal point thickness of the i^{th} layer $\left(\sum_{i=1}^3 h_k^i = h_k\right)$.

Figure 1 - Three-layer sandwich shell element - Geometry and displacement components

The strain components are defined in terms of the local coordinate system, in which the local derivatives of the displacements u' , v' and w' are obtained from the global derivatives of the displacements u , v , and w . The global derivatives of the displacements u , v and w are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{J}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \eta} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial \eta} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \zeta} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial \zeta} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial \zeta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{J} is the jacobian matrix as

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \zeta} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \zeta} & \frac{\partial z}{\partial \zeta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The strain matrix \mathbf{B} , relating the strain components in the local \mathbf{B} system to the element nodal variable, is evaluated in each layer

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}' = \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{B}_k \mathbf{d}_k \quad (7)$$

where d_i is the vector of nodal variables.

The constitutive matrix, relating the stress and strain components in each layer is defined as

$$\sigma' = D' \varepsilon' \quad (8)$$

where σ' stands for the stress vector $\sigma' = [\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{x'y}, \tau_{x'z}, \tau_{y'z}]^T$ and ε' stands for the strain vector

$\varepsilon' = [\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \gamma_{x'y}, \gamma_{x'z}, \gamma_{y'z}]^T$. The constitutive matrix of the material of a typical layer is defined as

$$D' = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Note that in the constitutive matrix shear-correction factors are not included. If the material principal axes are not parallel to local axes then a transformation procedure has to be performed.

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

Example 1: Simply-supported three-layer sandwich plate under uniform pressure

Validity of the finite element formulations of the present model is established by comparing results for sandwich problems with those available in the form of exact, closed and finite element solutions. This example is selected from Srinivas[21], in which a square plate, simply supported along all four edges is analysed for different material and layer thickness configurations. The plate is loaded by a transversely uniform adimensional pressure ($q=1.0$). The 8-noded Serendipity element is used through out, and the maximum stresses are evaluated at the gauss points. The adimensional span of the plate is $a=10.0$, the adimensional laminate thickness is $h=1.0$, and the plate was modeled with a 2×2 mesh in a quarter of the plate. The thickness of the three layers are h_1, h_2, h_3 . The adimensional core material characteristics are

$$D'_{1_{core}} = \begin{bmatrix} 3.802 & 0.879 & 0 \\ 0.879 & 1.996 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1.0 \end{bmatrix}, D'_{2_{core}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.608 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.015 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where $[D'_1]$ and $[D'_2]$ are the membrane/bending and shear submatrices of the core constitutive matrix[8,9].

The skins (layers 1 and 3) material characteristics are proportional to the core characteristics and are calculated using factors c_1 and c_3 , being these defined as

$$c_k = \frac{[D'_{ij}]_k}{[D'_{ij}]_{core}}, \quad k = 1, 3 \quad (11)$$

Five different cases are studied aiming to simulate several kind of sandwich configurations, such as an isotropic homogeneous laminate (case 1), a symmetric sandwich (cases 2 and 3) and non-symmetric sandwich (cases 4 and 5).

The following general observations are made from the results presented in tables 1-5 and figure 2:

(1) Deflection and inplane stresses are accurately predicted without refining the mesh, as the 2×2 mesh in a quarter plate gives sufficiently accurate results. (2) For non-symmetric sandwich, this model presents a better bending behaviour, with very accurate deflections. We can notice that in cases 4 and 5, the most difficult to model, the predicted inplane stresses are more accurate than those predicted by Barros[7] and Figueiras[8] and are very close to the exact values. (3) With the present model (without the use of shear correction factors) a very accurate prediction of transverse shear stresses can be directly achieved, in each middle-surface.

Table 1- Maximum in-plane stresses σ_x/q ($x,y=0$) and displacements (case 1) $h_1/h=0.1, h_2/h=0.8, h_3/h=0.1, c_1=1, c_3=1$

Source	In-plane stresses>--Layer 1-- --Core -- --Layer 3--							
	w*	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	
Srinivas[Exact]	181.05	36.012	28.538	28.538	-28.545	-28.545	-35.937	
Figueiras [8]	183.99	36.223	28.978	28.978	-28.978	-28.978	-36.223	
Barros[7]	181.22	35.693	28.560	28.560	-28.560	-28.560	-35.693	
Kirchhoff	168.38	36.098	28.878	28.878	-28.878	-28.878	-36.098	
Present Analysis	182.12	36.311	28.883	28.912	-28.912	-28.883	-36.311	
Error (%)	0.57	0.83	1.21	1.31	1.27	1.18	1.04	

$$w^* = \frac{w_{\max} G_{12}(\text{core})}{h q}$$

Table 2- Maximum in-plane stresses σ_x/q ($x,y=0$) and displacements (case 2) $h_1/h=0.1, h_2/h=0.8, h_3/h=0.1, c_1=10, c_3=10$

Source	In-plane stresses>--Layer 1-- --Core -- --Layer 3--							
	w*	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	
Srinivas[Exact]	41.906	65.332	48.857	4.903	-4.860	-48.609	-65.083	
Figueiras[8]	41.922	65.226	48.735	4.8735	-4.8735	-48.735	-65.226	
Barros[7]	41.980	63.247	54.020	5.4020	-5.4020	-54.020	-63.247	
Kirchhoff	31.241	66.953	53.563	5.3563	-5.3563	-53.563	-66.953	
Present Analysis	42.000	65.578	49.352	4.944	-4.944	-49.444	-65.571	
Error (%)	0.22	0.38	1.01	0.84	1.73	1.72	0.75	

Table 3- Maximum in-plane stresses σ_x/q ($x,y=0$) and displacements (case 3) $h_1/h=0.1, h_2/h=0.8, h_3/h=0.1, c_1=50, c_3=50$

Source	In-plane stresses>--Layer 1-- --Core -- --Layer 3--							
	w*	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	
Srinivas[Exact]	16.753	67.213	37.473	0.7682	-0.7419	-37.157	-66.900	
Figueira[8]	16.850	58.307	46.646	0.9330	-0.9330	-46.646	-58.307	
Barros[7]	16.812	58.069	46.463	0.9290	-0.9290	-46.463	-58.069	
Kirchhoff	6.762	72.457	57.966	1.1593	-1.1593	-57.966	-72.457	
Present Analysis	16.801	67.696	37.561	0.7501	-0.7501	-37.561	-67.696	
Error (%)	0.29	0.72	0.23	2.41	1.11	1.09	1.19	

Table 4- Maximum in-plane stresses σ_x/q ($x,y=0$) and displacements (case 4) $h_1/h=0.1, h_2/h=0.8, h_3/h=0.1, c_1=50, c_3=10$

Source	In-plane stresses>--Layer 1-- --Core -- --Layer 3--							
	w*	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	
Srinivas[Exact]	28.297	91.610	37.307	0.7647	-4.4503	-44.512	-55.207	
Figueiras [8]	28.432	82.238	47.287	0.9457	-4.6464	-46.464	-53.455	
Barros [7]	28.300	81.774	47.013	0.9404	-4.6193	-46.193	-53.148	
Kirchhoff	17.855	90.037	51.771	1.0354	-5.0871	-50.871	-58.524	
Present Analysis	28.254	91.909	38.164	0.7624	-4.483	-44.841	-55.465	
Error (%)	0.15	0.33	2.29	0.30	0.73	0.74	0.47	

Table 5- Maximum in-plane stresses σ_x/q ($x,y=0$) and displacements (case 5) $h_1/h=0.1, h_2/h=0.6, h_3/h=0.3, c_1=10, c_3=10$

Source	In-plane stresses σ_x/q (x,y=0)							
	w*	--Layer 1--		--Core--	--Layer 3--			
		Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	Top	Bottom	
Srinivas[Exact]	34.549	63.756	50.236	5.0409	-0.3360	-3.4028	-43.771	
Figueiras [8]	34.921	63.504	53.218	5.3218	-0.8407	-8.497	-39.354	
Barros [7]	34.706	63.061	52.856	5.2856	-0.8436	-8.436	-39.089	
Kirchhoff	25.342	67.060	56.199	5.6199	-0.8972	-8.9729	-41.559	
Present Analysis	34.570	64.169	50.876	5.1012	-0.5407	-3.853	-43.897	
Error (%)	0.06	0.65	1.27	1.20	60.92	13.23	0.29	

Figure 2 - Inplane and transverse shear stresses- case 5

Example 2: Clamped Quadratic Shell

A clamped quadratic shell with a centrally placed normal point load is analysed and the results compared with references [8] and [22]. The material of the shell is isotropic and has the following properties:

$$E_x = E_y = 30000; \nu_{xy} = 0.3; G_{xy} = G_{xz} = G_{yz} = 11540$$

The shell geometry and mesh are defined in figure 3, where the thickness is taken as $h=0.2$ and the span as $L=6.0$. Central displacement is presented in table 6 and maximum σ_x is plotted in figure 4. Good agreement with references [8] and [22] is obtained, specially in what concerns central displacement.

Table 6 - Central displacement

Source	Central Displacement ($\times 10^{-2}$)
Figueiras [8]	-0.265122
Huang [22]	-0.262757
Present Analysis	-0.263484

Figure 3 - Geometry and mesh of a clamped quadratic shell

Figure 4 - Comparison of x-stress

4. CONCLUSIONS

A very accurate model for sandwich shell finite element analysis is presented. This model is more accurate than Mindlin first-order shear-deformation model [7,8,9] and has a better performance than Kirchhoff models, specially in non-symmetric sandwich laminates. Both deflections and inplane stresses are precisely predicted. Transverse shear stresses are also very precisely predicted in each layer midsurface, with no need of shear correction factors, usually employed in first order shear deformation theories. The membrane-bending coupling effects, so typical of non-symmetric laminates are direct and accurately calculated with this formulation.

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